

THERMAL STRESSES AT A SURFACE OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES BY THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

A fiber-matrix interaction at the free surface of a uniaxial glass-fiber resin-matrix composite due to thermal loading is analyzed using the Finite Element Method (FEM). The fibers in the composite are assumed to be arranged in a regular array. Making use of symmetry boundary conditions only one cell of such an array is considered. Various meshing patterns are used for the numerical analysis, ranging from coarse to very fine, with minimum element size about a thousand times smaller than the fiber radius. The analysis reveals a very high and localized radial stress concentration at the fiber-matrix interface near the surface. This stress is compressive when the temperature increases and tensile when the temperature decreases from the stress free temperature. Therefore, favorable conditions for crack initiation are created during a cooling phase of a thermal fluctuation cycle. A careful investigation of the numerical results indicates stress singularities of the radial and hoop stress components exist on the surface at the interface.

INTRODUCTION

Micromechanics of the fiber-matrix interaction can be analyzed using equations of Continuum Mechanics for the composite constituents. These equations, which represent equilibrium, kinematics, and constitutive relations should be solved simultaneously for the fiber and the matrix materials. The solution must also satisfy composite boundary conditions and interfacial continuity requirements. Analytically, such a problem, is extremely difficult if a coupling effect between the directions parallel and perpendicular to the fiber is included, even assuming an elastic behavior of the composite and drastically simplifying the geometry. For example, a somewhat simpler problem of a separate fiber embedded in an infinite matrix under in-plane unidirectional stretching was analyzed in [1,2], where truncated series consisting of the Bessel and Henkel functions were used. These analyses, assuming other purely mathematical simplifications, indicated a complex stress distribution near the end of the fiber and a stress singularity at the free surface of the interface.

On the other hand, in order to provide practical rules for evaluation of the load transfer between fiber and matrix, various relatively simple analytical [3,4] or numerical [5,6] models have been proposed. These models incorporate several assumptions approximating the stress/deformation fields and neglect the stress singularity. Emphasis is primarily on the calculation of the shear

stress (the so called shear-lag model) because this stress component has been considered responsible for the fiber-matrix separation observed experimentally. However, experiments have also revealed excessive radial deformations in the vicinity of the fibers-matrix interface at the free surface [7,8]. These deformations cannot be related to the shear stresses. Also, cracks that appeared in this area seemed to have been triggered only by the temperature decrease, the temperature increase was apparently not initiating any cracking. If the shear stresses, as obtained from the simplified models, were solely responsible for this phenomenon, they would have had similar effects for either increasing or decreasing temperature. These and other experimental observations, which are difficult to explain with the simplified models, have indicated that perhaps more accurate modeling and analysis is required to understand and predict the behavior of composites experiencing temperature changes.

The fiber-matrix interaction is analyzed here using the FEM. This numerical method attempts to solve the complete set of the governing equations with all the stress/deformation components included. Accuracy of the analysis is evaluated by monitoring the stress continuity between the elements and on the composite boundary. In order to meet the accuracy requirements, and to detect large stress gradients near the free surface, a sophisticated meshing is required. Interpretation of the results obtained from the patterns of different mesh density permit the determination of a stress singularity at the free surface.

MODELING A CONTINUOUS FIBER COMPOSITE BY FEM

Despite all the progress in the capacity of computers, the use of the FEM still requires a careful balancing between the accuracy of the results and the necessary computational effort. Usually, this effort increases rather fast with the size of the numerical model and the density of its discretization. That is why some assumptions of a geometrical nature are necessary. Here we are interested mainly in the fiber-matrix interaction at the free surface. In order to focus on this subject, the composite is assumed to be arranged in a regular array. In reality, the fiber distribution is more random which should mainly effect load magnitudes carried by particular fibers. However, the assumption of a regular array should not change the nature of the load transfer from a particular fiber to the surrounding matrix. Such a transfer takes place, since a significant tension in the fiber at same distance from the surface caused by the temperature increase, for example, must be reduced to zero at the free surface. From the viewpoint of mechanics and for numerical convenience the composite may be divided into two distinct zones (Fig. 1a), the inner zone in which the load does not change with location along the fiber, and the end zone in which the load transfer mentioned above occurs and may cause significant stress gradients. Special attention is paid to the end zone here, where rapid variations in magnitude of

Figure 1. The fiber arrangement.

the stress components may be easily lost in the FEM analysis if the model meshing is not done carefully enough. The length of the composite in the z -direction (axial) is assumed sufficiently long to reach the inner zone. This zone is recognized by the fact that the shear stresses on the fiber-matrix interface become negligible. Making use of the symmetry surfaces of the regular array (Fig. 1a), the prism shown in Fig. 2a need only be considered. Due to the nature of the problem the cylindrical coordinate system is used throughout the paper with the stress components as denoted in Fig. 2b. Since the stress distribution in the prism was found to be 'almost' axisymmetric, axisymmetric models, which provide a substantial numerical advantage over 3-D general modeling, were also analyzed. Such models neglect the components $\tau_{r\theta}$

Figure 2. A cell of the regular array and the stress notation.

and $\tau_{r\theta}$ of the stress tensor, but permit a much more detailed discretization. Occasionally, the numerical models using the general and axisymmetric elements were compared demonstrating a good correlation between the results, as can be seen in Fig. 3. Here the variation of the radial stress, σ_r , along the free surface with the radial distance from the center of the fiber is shown. It is noteworthy that stress at the interface in the direction $\theta = 30^\circ$ is always slightly larger than in the direction $\theta = 0^\circ$ and also slightly larger than the stress obtained from the axisymmetric model,

Figure 3. Variation of σ_r with the radial distance along the free surface.

which assumes identical values along the circumference. Also, as it is shown in the next section, σ_r is a dominating stress component for the problem, so the differences between the general and axisymmetric results for the other stress components are less significant.

Figure 4. Details of meshing.

Preliminary numerical results have indicated that the stress magnitudes are very sensitive to meshing patterns in the vicinity of the free surface along the fiber-matrix interface, referred to as the FSI point in Fig. 4. In order to establish an appropriate pattern, the accuracy of each numerical model was verified in terms of the interelemental stress continuity and the residual stress values on the free surface. Theoretically, applying the h -convergence strategy, the accuracy can be improved by locally reducing the size of elements. This technique has led to a typical meshing pattern as shown in Fig. 4a. The elements with quadratic shape functions available from the ADINA and ANSYS software packages were used. Such elements admit a linear stress variation within the element volume. The meshing density in the vicinity of the FSI must be quite high to detect large stress gradients there[9]. If the ratio of the element size h to the fiber radius r , h/r , is greater than approximately $1/5$, the meshing almost completely overlooks any stress concentration. The analysis starts showing very high and very localized stresses at the FSI only if $h/r < 1/20$. The h/r ratio was varied from $1/3$ to $1/1000$. The meshing pattern for $h/r = 1/200$ is shown in Fig. 4a. In Fig. 4b the area around FSI was magnified 11 times to show the meshing details. Despite such a dense meshing, the accuracy of the elements immediately surrounding the FSI (elements A and B in Fig. 4c) was still not satisfactory. This

phenomenon is attributed to and explained by the presence of a stress singularity at the FSI, as discussed in the next section.

THE STRESS COMPONENTS NEAR THE SURFACE

The results presented here were obtained for a E-Cr glass-fiber and resin-matrix. The following elastic material properties were used (subscripts *f* and *m* denote fiber and matrix, respectively):

$$E_f = 77.2 \cdot 10^3 \text{ MPa}, \nu_f = 0.25, \alpha_f = 5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}$$

$$E_m = 2.41 \cdot 10^3 \text{ MPa}, \nu_m = 0.35, \alpha_m = 63 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/}^\circ\text{C}.$$

A range of fiber volume fraction from 6% to 60% was considered. Typical stress results are presented in Fig. 5 which have been obtained with the meshing shown in Fig. 4 for +50°C uniform temperature increase. At some distance from the free surface, roughly greater than the radius of the fiber, the axial stress, σ_z , and the shear stress, τ_{rz} , follow approximately the pattern

Figure 5. The stress variation along the fiber.

predicted by the shear-lag theory. The stress τ_{rz} becomes negligible around the distance $7r$ from the surface. This distance can be considered the depth of the end zone (Fig. 1a). Further away from the free surface, in the inner zone, the solution can be obtained assuming the plane-strain state, as in [5,6], with all stress/strain components being independent of the axial location z . The largest changes in stress take place at the very narrow layer of material near the surface. The large gradient of the shear stress τ_{rz} (which should drop to zero at the free surface) is accompanied by a rapid increase of the radial stress σ_r . The radial stresses were consistently much bigger than any other stress component throughout the whole analysis, including the shear stress. These radial stresses were tensile if the temperature decreased and compressive if the temperature increased. Since a typical bonding along the interface should be capable of carrying much higher stress in compression than in tension, the chance of initiating a crack during cooling is much greater than when warming. Also, the presence of the excessive radial strains, as reported in [7], is now self-explanatory.

THE STRESS SINGULARITY

Despite a very dense meshing at the FSI, the maximum stress values continuously increased with the further reduction of the element size. Also, the accuracy of the stress calculations of the elements adjacent to the FSI (elements A and B in Fig. 4a) was consistently poor. This is characteristic for situations where the FEM technique attempts to approximate a singular stress field using regular elements (with linear stress or strain variation, in this case). In such a field magnitudes of the stress components tend to infinity. It should be noted that the singular elements used in Fracture Mechanics are capable of simulating the singularities of type $\xi^{-1/2}$ or ξ^{-1} only (where ξ is a distance measured from the singular point). From the analytical solution presented in [1,2], and also from numerical experimentation, it was concluded that the singularity present in the case considered here is not of the type mentioned above. A numerical method, that permits determination of singularity type, was proposed and used in [9]. This method makes use of the fact that the magnitudes of the maximum radial and hoop stress components (at the FSI) increase continuously if the meshing parameter, h/r , decreases. This effect is shown in Fig. 6a. The type of singularity is determined by plotting the same results on a log-log scale (Fig. 6b) and

Figure 6. Variation of maximum σ_r with the meshing parameter h/r .

then calculating the slope of the line. A stress singularity very close to the type $\xi^{-1/2}$ (here ξ is the distance measured from the FSI) was found, and is independent of the volume fraction and the materials used. Since the elements with linear stress variation available from the ANSYS and ADINA programs use different number of integration points while calculating the stiffness matrix (ADINA uses 9 points, ANSYS uses 4 points), results obtained using these programs are shown for comparison and verification.

Some FEM results as well as the difficulties encountered when attempting to analyze the fiber-matrix interaction in a unidirectional continuous composite are presented. In order to determine characteristic features of this interaction, a relatively dense meshing at the free surface is required. The analysis reveals very large stress gradients near the surface. The radial stress component, which is usually overlooked in many reported investigations, seems to be dominant there. The magnitude of this stress, as obtained for a particular meshing pattern, results mainly from 'averaging' inherent in the FEM technique and should not be given any significant physical meaning. Investigating the accuracy of the solution on the element level and interpreting the sensitivity of the stress magnitudes versus the meshing parameters proves the presence of the stress singularity in this location. It is believed that this stress singularity, or rather its type, should somehow be related to the initiation and geometry of cracks observed on the surface.

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